

LandSeaLot Deliverable 4.1

Summary of the technical and community needs of LILs

26 July 2024/version 1.0

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

LandSeaLot has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No 101134575. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project LandSeaLot are supported by UKRI grant numbers: 10109592 University of Stirling and 10107554 Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

About this document

Title	D4.1, Summary of the technical and community needs of LILs
Work Package	WP4, Increasing the observation capacity
Lead Partner	Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Patrick Gorringer (SMHI) and Lucie Cocquempot (Ifremer)
Lead Author (Org)	Emilie Breviere (SMHI)
Contributing Author(s)	Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Maria Nordström (SMHI), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Mikael Stenström (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Giulia Dapuzeto (ETT), Antonio Novellino (ETT), Sampsa Koponen (Syke, Finnish Environment Institute), Irina Stanciu (GeoEcoMar), Adrian Stanica (GeoEcoMar), Andrew Tyler (University of Stirling), Peter Hunter (University of Stirling), Laurent Coppola (CNRS), Christophe Rabouille (CNRS), Costas Frangoulis (HCMR), Christina Papadaki (HCMR), Elias Dimitriou (HCMR), Debora Bellafore (CNR), Romaric Verney (Ifremer), Francisco Campuzano (+Atlantic), Yoana Voynova (Hereon), Anouk Blauw (Deltares)
Reviewers	Jos Brils (Deltares), Frank Lamé (Deltares)
Due Date	31.07.2024, M6
Submission Date	31.07.2024
Version	1.0

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

LandSeaLot: Land-Sea interface: Let's observe together! is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon Europe Work programme topics addressed: HORIZON-CL6-2023-01-11 : Reducing observation gaps in the land-sea interface area. Start date: 01 February 2024. End date: 31 January 2028.

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

LandSeaLot has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No 101134575. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project LandSeaLot are supported by UKRI grant numbers: 10109592 University of Stirling and 10107554 Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Method	6
3. Results	7
3.1. Community needs	10
3.2. Technology needs	10
3.3. Sensor evaluation needs	11
3.4. Collaboration opportunities	12
4. Conclusions	12
Annex 1. Notes of the 9 LILs interviews	14
LIL Baltic Sea interview	15
LIL Firth of Forth interview	16
LIL Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta interview	19
LIL North Aegean interview	21
LIL Po Delta and North Adriatic interview	24
LIL Seine Estuary and Bay interview	26
LIL Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary interview	30
LIL Tagus and Sado estuaries System interview	32
LIL Danube delta and coastal area interview	37

1. Introduction

Coastal regions sustain large populations and economies. Most of the blue economy activities are in the Land-Sea Interface area (LSI), with conflicting interests between fisheries, aquaculture, energy production, sub-seabed gas storage, tourism, leisure and transport. A key question is how to reconcile the necessity for ecosystem restoration, biodiversity conservation and climate adaptation with the need to provide more energy, food, and bioresources from the sea. Addressing this question requires an enhanced understanding of the environment, which can only be provided by dedicated observation platforms across a range of 'use cases' encompassing the geographical, economic, and environmental conditions observed in Europe. The LSI represents one of the most challenging areas for comprehensive observations, due to their strong variability in space and time. This large variability requires a combination of different observational approaches in the LSI. Since significant economic activity is concentrated at the coastal and estuarine environments, they are surrounded by densely populated areas. This provides a largely untapped resource of communities invested in their environment, with the potential to grow citizen science initiatives, citizen understanding of coastal regions and calls-to-action, and thus increase the number and coverage of *in situ* observations.

The overarching objective of LandSeaLot is to bring together interdisciplinary capabilities to study the LSI which will be achieved through integrating and enhancing existing coastal observation efforts -including *in situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science.

LandSeaLot approach is developed at the European level and piloted in selected local regions with local stakeholders: the LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LIL). These local studies will feed back experiences on feasibility and bottlenecks to the approach development.

Nine LILs in Europe have been selected to cover all European regional water bodies (Baltic, Mediterranean, and Black Seas, the North Sea and English Channel and the Atlantic coastal area). These include some of the most important riverine systems (Elbe, Rhine, Seine, Tagus, Rhone, Po, Nestos, Danube), as well as deltas and estuaries, in a range of physical environments, from micro to macro tidal systems (Fig. 1). High priority societal challenges have been identified for each LIL and some initial activities plans have been envisioned to address one or more of these priorities. The plans will be adapted based on stakeholders' interactions and feedback.

INTEGRATION LABS

Figure 1: Distribution of the 9 LandSeaLot Integration Labs in Europe

One of the seven specific objectives of LandSeaLot is to expand the number of *in situ* observations using low-cost observation technology, such as specific cheap but reliable sensors to be used via traditional scientific acquisition communities and/or citizen science engagement when applicable.

The aim of LandSeaLot Work Package (WP) 4 is to expand observing capacity through implementation and piloting of low-cost technologies and exploitation of citizen science programs in the LILs.

WP4 will provide the LILs with technical solutions to collect new *in situ* observations to close observation gaps in the LSI to address some of their specific societal challenges. The technical solutions are composed of low-cost technologies and/or citizen science activities to collect the data. Where applicable, citizen science communities, such as boaters in marinas, will be engaged. WP4 strongly links to, and is supported by WP6 'Data Management and Services' to guarantee an optimal and a long-term sustainable data flow to major data aggregators.

At the inception of the project, it was essential for WP4 to frame the LILs societal challenges in terms of observation capabilities that could increase knowledge. This deliverable is presenting a summary of those technical and community needs and opportunities.

2. Method

The WP4 partners considered a few possible approaches to collect information, such as online survey to complete or literature review. It was decided to carry out individual interviews for each LIL in order to establish a good communication flow between the WP and the LIL leads from the project inception. A one-hour interview was arranged with each leader and key participants of the 9 LILs.

They were conducted by SMHI with the participation of WP4 partners MARIS, ETT, SMHI, IFREMER and TEM and took place online in March and May 2024. Each interview was recorded for internal use and minutes were taken during the interview in case of recording failure. All interviews were carried out following a similar agenda and set of questions. The purpose of the interview was mentioned, and the discussion took place around 3 topics: 1) citizen science and communities, 2) cost effective technologies and 3) data landscape. The following questions in random order were asked to facilitate the exchange and ease the conversation:

- What are your data gaps? What are the benefits for you (closing those data gaps)?
- What do you need from a parameter point of view?
- Do you need a complete cost-effective solution from sensor to data collection? Or just sensors?
- Do you already have any low-cost sensors/cost efficient sensors in your area?
- Could your site be used as a comparison site/ test site to compare low cost sensors/cost efficient sensors to those commonly used?
- What are the societal challenges at your LIL?
- Are there citizen science initiatives in the LIL? Are you working with them?
- Are there communities that could potentially be approached to perform measurements with low-cost sensors?
- Are there marinas in your LIL?

Once the interview was carried out, the videos and minutes were reviewed and some structured notes were proposed to the LIL leaders interviewed for adjustments and to ensure that all information shared were well related.

3. Results

The dates and participants list of each interview are reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Date and participants list of the 9 LIL interviews

LIL interviewed	Interview date	Interviewed participants	LIL	WP4 participants attending the interview
Baltic Sea	3 May 2024	Sampsa Koponen (Syke, Finnish Environment Institute)		Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Maria Nordström (SMHI), Mikael Stenström (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM)
Danube delta and coastal area	20 May 2024	Irina Stanciu and Adrian Stanica (GeoEcoMar)		Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Mikael Stenström (SMHI)
Firth of Forth	8 March 2024	Andrew Tyler and Peter Hunter (University of Stirling)		Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Antonio Novellino (ETT), Giulia Dapuetto (ETT), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)

Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta	19 March 2024	Laurent Coppola, Christophe Rabouille (CNRS)	Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Giulia Dapuetto (ETT), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Melanie Symes (TEM), Lucie Cocquempot (Ifremer)
North Aegean	19 March 2024	Costas Frangoulis, Christina Papadaki, Elias Dimitriou (HCMR)	Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Mikael Stenström (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Lucie Cocquempot (Ifremer), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)
Po Delta and North Adriatic	3 May 2024	Debora Bellafiore (CNR)	Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Maria Nordström (SMHI), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Mikael Stenström (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Giulia Dapuetto (ETT)
Seine Estuary and Bay	1 March 2024	Romarc Verney (Ifremer)	Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Lucie Cocquempot (IFR), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)
Tagus and Sado estuaries System	20 March 2024	Francisco Campuzano (+Atlantic)	Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Giulia Dapuetto (ETT), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)
Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary	2 May 2024	Yoana Voynova (Hereon) and Anouk Blauw (Deltares)	Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Maria Nordström (SMHI), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Mikael Stenström (SMHI)

All interviews' notes are available in Annex 1.

In the interview plans, there were 3 points of discussion, citizen science and communities, low-cost sensors and data landscape. The last point was to gather information contributing to deliverable D6.1 'Data landscape report' from WP6 on Data Management and Services. It emerged rapidly after a couple of interviews that it was too early in the LILs scientific development to collect concrete information about the data landscape in the LILs, and that sometimes the key data persons involved in the LIL were not present at the interviews. Additionally, the interview discussions focussing on WP4 topics were not suitable to collect information of all the type of data which will be used in the LIL (Earth observations, classic *in situ* observations and model outputs). To address those short comings, it was then decided that the most appropriate way to collect the needed information for D6.1 was to produce a table template with key entries including examples for each entry and each possible type of data for clarity. The template will be circulated to each LIL for completion. These completed tables will contribute to D6.1.

The notes have been analysed and an overview of the LIL needs in terms of communities and low-cost sensors is proposed in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of the LILs needs in terms of communities and cost-effective technologies

LIL	COMMUNITIES		LOW-COST TECH NEEDS	
	Citizen Science/ community	Marina	Sensor needs	Parameters needs if sensor exist
BALTIC SEA	Not the priority interest of the LIL. Community and citizen science landscape has not been assessed prior to the interview.	No connection with the marinas	Not planned (high accuracy is required)	IN RIVER: -turbidity -discharge -water level -nutrients -carbon
FIRTH OF FORTH	Existing links with 2 communities associations that could serve as intermediaries: -Forth rivers trust -Scottish flood forum	No connection with the marinas	-Temperature sensors in rivers to contribute to the Scotland River Temperature Monitoring Network	-Water temperature -Water quality -freshwater biodiversity -carbon -turbidity -conductivity
GULF OF LIONS, RHONE DELTA	Via RIOMar: -Astrolabe-Expeditions, NGO, sailing boats measure temperature and salinity with self-built sensors. Opportunity to export the activity from Britany to the LIL -Biodiversity French Agency, public agency, could serve as link to communities	No connection with the marinas	-Salinity via the Astrolabe-Expeditions, SensOcean programme	-salinity -fluorescence -oxygen -pH
NORTH AEGEAN	-REMEDIES, Cyclades demonstration site -Plastic Pirates: Go Europe -communities fisherman, sailors	No connection with the marinas	-macroplastics flow counted by cameras under bridges in river (x3 locations) -microplastic flow via nets deployed by communities and/or camera (x4 locations) -chl-a, turbidity, oxygen, conductivity sensors with a low-cost buoy (x2 locations) - several low-cost conductivity sensors - a portable TUR/FLU sensor for onsite check of the deployed buoys sensors.	IN RIVER: -water level -Nutrient
PO DELTA	Citizen science initiatives existing are not relevant for the LIL activities.	No connection with the marinas but in front of the Venice Lagoon, the Venice marina could be approached.	Not planned (high accuracy is required)	-salinity in the last 30km of the mouth inland -Salinity measured at the bottom. -water level, wave height -carbon
SEINE ESTUARY AND BAY	Involving marinas in citizen science initiative Phenomer	Connection with Le Havre marina (dredging)	-turbidity -fluorescence -chlorophyll-a -temperature, -salinity	

			-nutrients	
TAGUS AND SADO ESTUARIES SYSTEM	-Aquaculture farms -Portuguese environmental agency	Connection with marinas via the port of Lisbon	-temperature loggers (x50-100units) -water level (2-4 units) - cameras (6 units) - realtime water level and temperature	-pressure (logger type) - salinity - nutrients - chlorophyll
WADDEN SEA, RHINE DELTA AND ELBE ESTUARY	-SOOP -Implementation of Phenomer concept to the LIL	No connection but marinas could be approached.	Not planned	-pH -carbon
DANUBE DELTA AND COASTAL AREA	-remote villages communities	No connection with the marinas	-water level -salinity -turbidity -chlorophyll -temperature -marine litter -microplastics	

3.1. Community needs

Citizen Science refers to the general public engagement in scientific research activities. There are multiple forms of participation, from problem detection to solution proposal, via data collection and analysis. The topics tackled by the citizen science initiatives are also very diverse, they range from biology to physics.

To address their societal challenges, the LILs, **North Aegean** and **Seine Estuary and Bay**, need to access observation data collected by citizen engaged in scientific activities. Each LIL lead is involved in known established citizen science initiatives. They expressed the wish to either provide to them (NGOs, university, Plastic Pirates: Go Europe) additional devices or to add to their initiative another community which is not yet engaged (boaters from marinas in Phenomer).

The LILs **Tagus and Sado Estuaries System** and **Firth of Forth**, will benefit from public organisations engaging as citizen scientists, such as the Portuguese Environmental Agency and the Scotland River Temperature Monitoring Network, thus establishing a mutually benefiting collaboration. The **Tagus and Sado Estuaries System** LIL is also engaging aquaculture farmers.

Despite a large number of citizen science initiatives in the **Po Delta** LIL, none is collecting data on a societal challenge addressed by LandSeaLot.

The LIL **Baltic Sea** plans to use existing professional automated measurement observations and the opportunity of citizen science is not investigated.

The LILs, **Wadden Sea, Rhine Delta and Elbe Estuary; Seine Estuary and Bay** and **Danube Delta and coastal area**, present some opportunities, they could propose to implement in their LILs citizen science programmes (Astrolabe-Expeditions and Phenomer respectively for the first two LILs) currently performed in other areas than their LILs.

3.2. Technology needs

To address their societal challenges, four LILs, **North Aegean, Tagus and Sado Estuaries System, Seine Estuary and Bay** and **Firth of Forth** rely on the procurement of cost-effective devices. They

are interested in different types of sensors measuring different parameters, such as plastics, nutrients, temperatures, conductivity, fluorescence, oxygens, water levels and turbidity (Table 2).

The six LILs with challenges requiring carbon system and/or nutrients data have a lower need of cost-effective technologies. It is common knowledge that currently there are not yet efficient operating sensors for these parameters. However, all are eager to test devices if any emerge and appear promising, the parameters they would be interested to measure are listed in the right column of Table 2.

The **Po Delta** and **Baltic Sea** LILs, have mentioned that they need measurements with high level of accuracy, which low-cost sensors cannot provide.

The LILs **Wadden Sea, Rhine Delta and Elbe Estuary; Danube Delta and coastal area** and **Gulf of Lions, Rhone Delta** plan to address their societal challenges based primarily on knowledge supported by observations provided by other methods than the one supplied by community and cost-efficient technology. They primarily rely on data issue from modelling, remote sensing or traditional ocean observation technics

However, the LIL **Gulf of Lions, Rhone Delta** would encourage and support the implementation of the citizen science activity Astrolabe-Expeditions in the LIL, to measure salinity with cost-effective sensors.

3.3. Sensor evaluation needs

All LILs in need of deploying low-cost sensors shared concerns about the sensor evaluation. They mentioned that before being deployed, the sensors need to be tested, in the LIL or somewhere else. They asked how this can be implemented.

From the interviews performed, it emerged that 5 LILs could offer lab facilities or *in situ* facilities (vessel, mooring points, infrastructure) to test cost-effective sensors (Table 3).

Table 3: Summary of the LILs facilities to test/evaluate cost-effective technologies

LIL	Potential testbed
BALTIC SEA	
FIRTH OF FORTH	Forth ERA from river to sea.
GULF OF LIONS, RHONE DELTA	
NORTH AEGEAN	River monitoring station measuring discharge, basic physical and chemical parameters (pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen and water temperature)
PO DELTA	
SEINE ESTUARY AND BAY	-Ifremer sea field campaigns -DYNECO/DHYSED lab facilities (turbidity in particular, but also Chl-a and nut)
TAGUS AND SADO ESTUARIES SYSTEM	-tower structure south of Setubal
WADDEN SEA, RHINE DELTA AND ELBE ESTUARY	-station Cuxhaven, Hereon river station, Tesperhude Research Station and shallow water vessel as test beds via AQUARIUS
DANUBE DELTA AND COASTAL AREA	

Thus, WP4 identified that a testing and evaluation procedure needs to be investigated, shared and decided upon. Multiple options, including testing in one or more LILs, depending on parameters and locations, are possible and will be considered.

3.4. Collaboration opportunities

The interviews highlighted that in some of the LILs there could be a mutual beneficial cooperation possible between LandSeaLot and other projects and organisations active in the LIL. Collaboration between LandSeaLot and those projects would contribute to a synergetic approach to the cost-effective observation strategy in the coastal zone and will be encouraged. The existing connections mentioned by the LIL leads during the interviews are listed in Table 4. It is to note that this list is only a sample of potential collaborations and not exhaustive. More potential collaborations will be identified during the project lifetime.

Table 4: Summary of the LILs potential synergies with projects and organisations.

LIL	Project/organisation for potential collaboration
BALTIC SEA	
FIRTH OF FORTH	-SenseH2O (project) -CENSIS (org)
GULF OF LIONS, RHONE DELTA	-RIOMar (project)
NORTH AEGEAN	-REMEDIES (project) -Plastic Pirates: Go Europe (project) -local university
PO DELTA	
SEINE ESTUARY AND BAY	
TAGUS AND SADO ESTUARIES SYSTEM	-Portuguese Environmental Agency (governance) - Porto de Lisboa & Setubal (Ports and Marinas) - Associação Portuguesa de Aquacultura - local universities - Coastnet project - FOCCUS (project)
WADDEN SEA, RHINE DELTA AND ELBE ESTUARY	-SOOP (project) -AQUARIUS (project) -University Twente project in the flat tidal of the Wadden sea
DANUBE DELTA AND COASTAL AREA	-DOORS (project)

4. Conclusions

- The **North Aegean, Tagus and Sado Estuaries System, Seine Estuary and Bay** and **Firth of Forth** expressed strong needs in terms of cost-effective technologies to measure temperature, turbidity, water level and plastic amounts because they have no pre-existing measurements or because they have a need to increase the resolution of the data map in their area of interest.
- Almost all LILs expressed an interest in testing some sensors, even when their main source of data is issued from methods such as remote sensing, modelling or traditional ocean observations measurements.
- The LILs **Seine Estuary and Bay** and the **Tagus and Sado estuaries system** have been identified as the most promising with regard to engagement of the marinas boaters in collecting data, thanks to existing connection with the marinas and our partner TransEurope Marinas.

- The information collected with regard to parameters of interest and community needs will be used to set the framework for the selection of the low-cost technologies and/or citizen science projects/communities to engage.

Annex 1. Notes of the 9 LILs interviews

LIL Baltic Sea interview

with Sampa Koponen (Syke, Finnish Environment Institute)
on 3 May 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Maria Nordström (SMHI), Mikael Stenström (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

Baltic Sea (B): The evaluation of carbon budgets in the Baltic area is hampered by high uncertainties in the influx of carbon from land. In this LIL, improved EO algorithms will be coupled with numerical models, automated and manual *in situ* observations and isotope analysis to qualify and quantify carbon fluxes at river mouths. The impact of heatwaves on cyanobacteria blooms and dissolved carbon degradation will be evaluated by coupling merged EO SST products and *in situ* low-cost temperature observations with biogeochemical observations.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

Currently, the LIL plans to rely on their existing professional automated measurement observations and modeling. But if in the coming year or so, there is a sensor that shows promise with good measurement characteristics, it would be considered.

At the time of the interview, the LIL group has not yet met and further planned their activities.

1. **Communities**

No plan to engage with citizen science initiatives or community at this stage.

2. **Low-cost tech**

In this LIL, high accuracy is needed.

In rivers, there are sensors for turbidity, discharge, water level and more to estimate nutrients, phosphorus, nitrogen, carbon... Different rivers have different sensors. Chlorophyll, turbidity and temperature are also estimated from Earth observations.

Low-cost instruments could be considered to get more observations and in places more easily accessible by communities and low-cost sensors. Ideas of the fisherman community along the Swedish coast using Probe sensors.

3. **Data landscape**

The topic was not discussed during the interview.

LIL Firth of Forth interview

with Andrew Tyler and Peter Hunter (University of Stirling)
on 8th March 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Antonio Novellino (ETT), Giulia Dapueto (ETT), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

Firth of Forth (FF): Building a digital observatory towards a fully developed digital twin, this LIL will focus on carbon landscapes, water quality and quantity across the catchment to coast continuum, using next generation sensors and sensor networks, contributing to interoperability issues, data assimilation and data fusion. It will also focus on floods from land, droughts, building on existing capabilities, integrating data (SAR & optical EO, *in situ* data from echosounding, tide gauges, wave and water quality buoys, above water radiometry, soil moisture, hydrodynamic and hydrology models, low-cost water level sensors), in order to understand the full water continuum.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

In the Firth of Forth, the environment and climate are changing, and the effects are felt largely through water, extreme events, floods and droughts as well as shifts in water quality, consequently, shifts in ecology. There is a need to understand better the system. However existing data across the catchments are compartmentalized and it is difficult to get access to it. There is therefore a need to get the data together hence the establishment of the digital observatory Forth ERA. Data gaps exist too.

The [Forth ERA](#) (Environmental Resilience Array) is a large-scale digital observatory for the Firth of Forth catchment co-developed with stakeholders (industry, statutory agencies...). It is a platform that is combining observations from sensor networks, from satellite observations, models, trying to improve the way that monitoring, and management of the environment are performed. Peter Hunter is the science director of the Forth ERA. The Forth ERA is working across a number of thematic application areas, including floods and droughts and water quality, as well as people and restoration, biodiversity and air quality. The Forth ERA will be a super site in the DANUBIUS Research Infrastructure for river-sea systems.

1. **Communities**

The Port Edgar marina is not a stakeholder of the Forth ERA, but it has charter vessels from the marina.

- Community umbrella organisations

In the LIL, there are some very active community groups, such as CSO safari (citizen society organisation looking at the storm flow out of wastewater treatment works, spills raw sewage into rivers), or anglers and surfers active too. But they are not well organised, they run sometimes ad-hoc data collection campaigns. No large-scale citizen science initiatives per se exist but there are a couple of organisations which have well established connections with citizen groups, communities, companies, industries and businesses in the catchment, with trust and dialogue in place:

- Forth rivers trust (forthriverstrust.org). Andrew and Peter have a very active engagement with this well-respected organisation.
- Scottish flood forum (<https://scottishfloodforum.org/>). Some of the groups coordinated by the forum are already working with river tracks sensors (<http://rivertrack.org/>). They would likely be interested in looking into new cost-effective technologies.

These organisations could facilitate the dialogue between the LIL leads and the groups if the LIL were to consider engaging one into taking measurements with a sensor during one of their campaigns as a trial. It could form a nice citizen-science collaboration showcase. Andrew and Peter will need to look into what group(s) would make sense to approach with regard to the LIL data needs, which data gap could be closed.

2. Low-cost tech

• Test bed:

In the Forth ERA, commercial instruments measuring water level, flow and quality are deployed though the entire catchment. The Forth ERA could be used as a testbed for comparison of low-cost sensors purchased by LandSeaLot to those traditional instruments.

• Project collaboration and synergetic approach

Thanks to a grant from NERC and Defra, the Forth ERA is working on developing low-cost sensors with the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency and Scottish Waters. Within the project SenseH2O (A scalable, integrated systems-based approach to monitoring water quality from headwaters to river outlets, <https://www.ukri.org/news/uk-invests-in-monitoring-of-natural-environment/>), they work with the organisation CENSIS (<http://censis.org.uk>). CENSIS is Scotland's Innovation Centre for sensing, imaging and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. CENSIS is well connected with sensors manufacturers and developers' community in the UK. It could be a good opportunity for collaboration across projects. Peter and Andrew are also working with some companies making low-cost sensors:

RiverTrack on river level sensors <http://rivertrack.org/>

SouthWestSensor www.southwestsensor.co.uk

Lightwater sensors <https://lightwatersensors.com/>

ClearWater Sensors <https://www.clearwatersensors.com/>

• Integration of LandSeaLot cost-effective sensor data to the Forth ERA digital observatory: closing data gaps in the Firth of Forth

The Firth of Forth presents some monitoring data gaps (water temperature, water quality, freshwater biodiversity, blue carbon...) that cost-effective sensors could possibly cover. It would form an interesting showcase if those data could be included in the Forth ERA digital observatory.

Some of the data gaps are actually fundamental, on fairly basic parameters such as water temperature (the current measurement frequency is not high enough across the catchment). Turbidity and conductivity are also of interest.

For instance, the [Scotland River Temperature Monitoring Network](#) has sensors deployed across a number of large catchments in Scotland. The network used to have sensors deployed across the Forth, the data was collected by people visiting the sensors. Due to resource issue (cost and power requirements of the telemetry), the network is no longer maintained in the Forth. Discussion is ongoing with the Marine directorate of the Forth to replace the sensors by low-cost sensors over time.

In LandSeaLot, there is a data management component that could be used to set up data flows from the sensor to the aggregators (EMODnet, Copernicus), if not existing or partially existing to make the data useful. The data flow will depend on the sensor used.

3. **Data Landscape**

There is some outflow data from DANUBIUS in EMODnet, but no supplementary data from the sites. At the Forth ERA site, water level and flow, and water quality from the headwaters to the mouth of the Forth Estuary will be measured. Those data could be linked to EMODnet physics.

LIL Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta interview

with Laurent Coppola, Christophe Rabouille (CNRS)
on 19 March 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Giulia Dapuzo (ETT), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Melanie Symes (TEM), Lucie Cocquemot (Ifremer)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta (GRL): This LIL, as part of a JERICO-RI region, engages experts from several disciplines to evaluate carbon budgets and pCO₂ fluxes in these highly variable regions of river plumes and adjacent areas, which are strongly impacted by climate change and anthropogenic pressures. Neural network methods integrating simulations of the physical-biogeochemical model (e.g., SYMPHONIE), satellite SST and Chl-a products and *in situ* observations will be piloted to provide a combined information product on CO₂ budgets ranging from the river mouth to the coastal sea.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

RIOMar is a French national project (<https://riomar.lsce.ipsl.fr/>) that aims to build an original integrated approach combining augmented observatories, innovative digital tools and model simulations to anticipate the future of coastal marine ecosystems. One of the 5 coastal areas studied is the Gulf of Lions and Rhone River. Christophe Rabouille is the PI.

Astrolabe-Expeditions is a citizen science initiative that develops their cost-effective sensors.

1. Citizen science / communities

- Astrolabe-Expeditions (<https://www.astrolabe-expeditions.org/>) is an association, NGO involved in RIOMar. This citizen science initiative proposes 5 different scientific programmes for recreational sailors. SensOcean is one of them, on measurement of physical parameters (T and S). Instruments needed for the measures are built by the association and the citizens, then deployed on the citizen sailing boats (fleet of 10-15 boats). Cedric Courson is the association president (cedric.courson@astrolabe-expeditions.org). Within RIOMar, the association is only involved in south Brittany, but could consider developing its activity in the Gulf of Lions and Rhone River, pending funding.

- The LILs end-users and their needs are:

- Within RIOMar, work is ongoing with the Biodiversity French Agency (OFB, <https://www.ofb.gouv.fr/en>) the public institution dedicated to the protection and restoration of biodiversity. The agency is interested in the development of indicators of ocean health and biodiversity. It is a key actor of RIOMar as it links with other end-users communities such as Marine Protected Areas and facilitate the connections of scientists and communities to work on topics like marine heatwaves impacts, augmented observatories for DNA sensors...
- Ocean literacy, mediation with schools and teachers are also relevant as educational end-users. Villefranche-sur-mer is active (Culture Ocean, Adopt floats...).
- Fishery is also relevant in this LIL, the fisherman community is large but few contacts exist for the moment and communication could be improved.

- Offshore windfarms are also important end-users. There are ongoing scientific projects to monitor the area around the wind turbines to study their impact on the marine ecosystems.

- There are no marinas' members in this LIL.

2. Low-cost tech

- In the LIL area, there is an experience of cost-effective moorings, 3 have been deployed in Jan 2024 and should be recovered in April 2024. The Mastodon mooring system (<https://archimer.ifremer.fr/doc/00292/40319/>) developed by Ifremer consists of a shallow seafloor mooring equipped with cost-effective sensors. It may have a vertical line that allows for vertical profile measurements.

This eco-moorings may theoretically also be used by marinas boaters, but this should be confirmed by Ifremer as originally it has been developed for scientific applications.

- The French company Seaber (<https://seaber.fr/>) based in Lorient developed a cost-effective micro-AUV (Autonomous Underwater Vehicle) named YUCO (<https://seaber.fr/why-yuco-is-unique>), which is good to measure in estuary and shallow water areas. It is complimentary to gliders and will be deployed in the Med Sea within RIOMar (contact Ivane Pairaud, Ifremer)

- The temperature and salinity sensors developed by Astrolabe-Expeditions could be of interest, in particular the salinity one. Salinity is still a parameter difficult to have measured by low-cost sensor because often the precision is poor and the sensor lacks stability. As RIOMar study area is coastal area influenced by fresh water, the salinity gradient expected is rather large, larger than the salinity gradient in the open sea. So the accuracy and precision does not need to be high, which allows the Astrolabe-Expeditions to concentrate on fixing the sensor calibration. To cope with this, RIOMar proposed to the Astrolabe-Expeditions sailors to sail near the classic calibrated buoys/moorings in order to validate and/or calibrate their sensors. Another way to calibrate that has been discussed is that sailors collect water samples. Astrolabe-Expeditions is interested in developing fluorescence and oxygen sensors in the future, using commercialized measurement heads.

- Oxygen and pH sensors are interesting for the LIL challenge around CO₂. Nowadays with neural networks, pCO₂ can be predicted with oxygen and pH measurements.

3. Data landscape

The topic was not discussed during the interview.

LIL North Aegean interview

with Costas Frangoulis, Christina Papadaki, Elias Dimitriou (HCMR)
on 19 March 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Mikael Stenström (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Lucie Cocquempot (Ifremer), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

North Aegean (NA): This area is strongly threatened by plastic and nutrient pollution due to the human pressure on catchments and inputs from the Dardanelles straits. NA LIL is supported by JERICO-RI, ICOS-ERIC, DANUBIUS-RI and national (HIMIOFOTS) RIs and facilities to evaluate integrated approaches to inform on plastic pathways from rivers to the sea and on the effect of nutrients inputs on the trophic status of the ecosystem. It will link low-cost observation systems and citizen actions together with numerical Lagrangian simulations which will be improved by EO products assimilation.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

In the LIL, there are 4-5 rivers, HCMR concentrates on the Evros River which is the largest one because of project resource and time constraint. In the Evros River, there is a monitoring station measuring discharge, basic physical and chemical parameters (pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen and water temperature). Parameters are measured every hour and used in the HCMR model. In rivers, commercial instruments from the company In-situ (<https://in-situ.com/en/>) are usually used to measure the water level and the physical and chemical parameters, efficient however still costly. Low-cost ultrasonic sensors built by HCMR are also used to measure water levels as an experiment.

Data gaps in the LIL are on microplastics and macroplastics, and basic physical and chemical parameters in the coastal area in order to connect the two models and calibrate the marine component.

1. **Communities**

• Communities

HCMR has contacts with local NGOs familiar with the rivers and the area, municipality officials connected to the rivers and local university. Prefecture and university could be interested, in particular in the topic of flooding.

• Synergy with REMEDIES

REMEDIES is an EU-funded project (<https://remedies-for-ocean.eu/>) which works on (micro)plastics. The Cyclades (220 islands in Aegean Sea) is a demonstration site with underwater and aerial drones used to monitor microplastics and the pathways of plastics in the Aegean Sea. Citizen science initiatives are used via beach clean ups and social activities in collaboration with local schools, fishermen, municipalities and NGOs. REMEDIES has 8 demonstration sites in the Mediterranean Sea.

- Synergy with Plastic Pirates Go Europe

HCMR is partner in the EU-funded project Plastic Pirates Go Europe (<https://www.plastic-pirates.eu/en>), Greece is a study country. Samples are collected from rivers based on the project protocols, with a net provided. The samples are analysed in a lab at HCMR headquarters.

2. Low-cost tech

- Macroplastics flow (via camera)

There will be installed cameras under bridges to count macroplastics flow. The data will be used to force the models. Elias already tested the cameras and has the necessary operating software. However, the plastics detection algorithm will be tested and selected after the installation of the cameras.

At the time of the proposal, it was mentioned that probably 3 cameras would be needed to cover the entire width of the river.

- Microplastics flow (via nets or camera)

The LIL need is to get data on microplastics flow to validate the models. The information could be captured thanks to a camera if a low cost one exists (the LIL would be open to test it) or via a net to collect samples. The nets would be deployed close to the coast in 4 points (e.g. near the delta, near a city water discharge and 2 control areas) to allow the validation of the circulation in the model and 1 in the Evros river to capture the flow. Ideally the nets should be compact, small easy to handle, in order for fishermen or sailors communities to deploy them. Nets can be purchased but often Costas built them as it is a lot cheaper.

- Low-cost buoys

The buoys will be tested thanks to a TNA with the company Elements Community (<https://www.elements.community/pages/neth2o>) in the coming months. The contact with the company is good. They can adapt the buoys to different sensors as long as they have serial interface and power. For chl-a, and turbidity HCMR will likely need a specific sensor adapted to the LIL eutrophic waters. A sensor to measure oxygen would be useful too.

Comment post-interview from LIL leaders: *'We are considering also using several low-cost conductivity sensors and a portable TUR/FLU sensor for onsite check of the deployed buoys sensors.'*

SYKE (Finland) and HCMR will build on previous successful collaboration to select the appropriate sensors for this LIL. Three chl sensors are currently considered. The buoy company Elements Community will integrate the selected sensor to the buoy. And then the buoy needs to be tested.

At the time of the proposal writing, it was mentioned that the LIL needs 2 buoys.

- Water level in rivers

In the river, a low-cost sensor measuring water level such as the one that is plugged under a bridge, could be considered to intercompare with the Ebuilt low-cost one and the commercial instrument.

- Nutrients

Measuring nutrients would also be interesting and if cost effective sensors exist HCMR would be happy to test them in the LIL.

- Marine intercomparison

When marine intercomparisons are done, it is in the lab or in the field near the HCMR facilities in Athens or in Crete, not in the LIL area. For Example, HCMR is testing a prototype for CO₂ measurements which uses Artificial Intelligence from the company In-Situ, they test it against HCMR CO₂ sensors.

For the River, the monitoring station is in the LIL.

- Sensor testing

From experience there is a need to test sensors before they are deployed. In LandSeaLot, there is no testing procedure yet established. This is a strategy that will be investigated, shared and decided upon. Multiple options, including test beds in LILs, depending on parameters or locations, are possible and each will be considered.

3. **Data landscape**

HCMR is a National Oceanographic Data Center (HNODC) and the workflow of marine data is well set up to reach aggregators, such as EMODnet and Copernicus. Leonidas Perivoliotis is involved in the LandSeaLot Work Package 6 on Data. The river monitoring station data is public and online, part is sent to EFAS and the other part is sent to EMODnet.

LIL Po Delta and North Adriatic interview

with Debora Bellafiore (CNR)

on 3 May 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Maria Nordström (SMHI), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Mikael Stenström (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Giulia Dapuzeto (ETT)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

Po Delta and North Adriatic (PNA): Three RIs (DANUBIUS-RI, JERICO-RI, ICOS-ERIC) in the area will team up in this LIL to assess lateral carbon fluxes from its distributed riverine system and to address also flood risk from sea due to storm surges and increased saltwater intrusion, which impacts the Po River delta. The latter is a major environmental and socio-economic threat (e.g., water supply, agriculture). Regarding saltwater intrusion, the LIL will test the coupling of data streams from fixed instruments and EO imagery and EO algorithm development in order to obtain a surface salinity proxy based on field data and high resolution EO. For storm surge, model improvements through assimilation techniques will be used.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

The LIL participants decided to concentrate on the integration of the 3 different RIs. The co-presence of the 3 RIs and their full interaction in this LIL is quite peculiar among all the LILs.

1. **Communities**

In this LIL, it seems that the marinas are far from the geographical areas where the LIL activities are defined as per today, but it will be discussed with the Italian association (Mel). However, if activities were to develop also along the coastline in front of the Venice Lagoon, the Venice marina could be considered.

There are citizen science initiatives in the LIL but they are dealing with other topics, such as monitoring plastics, connection with biodiversity...

2. **Low-cost tech**

This LIL has no immediate need for low-cost sensors due to the following reasons: The North Adriatic is one of the most densely monitored areas, national and local authorities are measuring all sorts of parameters. Therefore, despite the need to increase the data pool and coverage, it is even more pressing to assure high accuracy of the data, at least harmonized to fixed classical sensors.

Furthermore, some of the LIL activities are going into the river where there is a monitoring station connected with the regional EPA. The station is 90 km inland, which is essential for the model to characterise the discharges. The idea is to include some equipment coming also from other projects and putting it in connection to increase the data availability. In particular, a radiometer will be installed there, hoping to have in the near future the authorization for installation, which will increase information from the source.

However, low-cost sensors could be interesting for the following points:

- The saltwater intrusion challenge is another particularity of this LIL among all the others, therefore a sensor to measure salinity in the last 30km of the mouth inland could be beneficial.
- To properly assess saltwater intrusion from the salinity, it should be measured at the bottom. But the LIL does not have a fixed bottom sensor for salinity. So to cope with this lack, the LIL participants will investigate other possible proxy for saltwater intrusion. They will check surface chlorophyll-a measurements from Earth Observations, which could be used to classify the different water masses. They could envision to consider other variables too depending on what the cost-effective sensors catalogue proposes.
- Another activity of the LIL is related to storm surge and flooding. The storm surge model will be connected to a long shore camera, which is already in place thanks to the region Emilia-Romagna. One option is that the study takes place at the Po delta and south of it. Presently, a second option is evaluated (based on the capability to use a non low-cost camera, similar to the ones deployed by Emilia Romagna EPA South of the Po Delta) on the shoreline in front of Venice to monitor the coastline variations and therefore detect effects on flooding and coastline due to storms. Added to this, two other types of measurements can be considered to track the flooded area inland (easily done with the Lido island of 1km wide) and the water level with wave heights on the sea side (Acqua alta oceanographic tower, 15 km offshore). This could open cooperation with the marinas. But as the Venice marina is located in the Lagoon, far from the Po and far from the platform used for the 3rd activity on Carbon lateral fluxes, it will not be looked at right away but most likely within the first year of LandSeaLot. Also, one should note that it takes time to buy and install instruments, obtain authorisations in Italy, so it might be interesting to investigate the citizen science landscape to see how those initiatives could support the activity.

The cost-effective sensor measuring water level in the catalogue as now is an ultrasonic instrument that can be plugged under a bridge. So it provides hydrographic level that could lead to discharges, it is fundamental but different from water level 100s m far from the coast which gives an indication on storm arriving. The sensor could be installed on existing platforms but as it would be challenging then it would decrease the cost effectiveness.

- The LIL 3rd activity is on carbon lateral fluxes or more generally carbon fluxes assessment at sea as the ICOS station Paloma located along the coast will be used. It will give the state of the very northern area of the North Adriatic. The North Adriatic has several medium or small dimensions rivers which provide 20 to 30% of fresh water. Carbon monitoring in the river is however missing, so if a cost-effective sensor measuring carbone is available it would be interesting. Additional data coming from the Acqua alta oceanographic tower (DANUBIUS RI but with cooperation of the other RIs) will be used, the station is located 15km far from the Venice lagoon. It would be a showcase of the different RIs.

3. Data landscape

The topic was not discussed during the interview.

LIL Seine Estuary and Bay interview

with Romaric Verney (Ifremer)

on 1st March 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringe (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Lucie Cocquempot (IFR), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)

Interview video recorded for internal purposes only.

Extract from the LandSeaLot proposal:

Seine Estuary and Bay (SEB): The Seine LIL is highly impacted by nutrient inputs from the catchment areas and heavy engineering work done to promote and maintain maritime traffic and economic development along the Seine estuary. Estuarine habitats and services are also highly threatened by consequences of climate change. Their impact on the ecosystem functioning will be investigated, including phytoplankton bloom dynamics, sediment fluxes and morphological evolutions and habitat modifications. LIL activities will include: i) the coupling of JERICO-RI observation networks and ocean colour data to evaluate merged, dynamically calibrated multi-sensor EO products on suspended solid concentration (SSC) and Chla; ii) the extension of a citizen science initiative for alerting and identifying blooms and engaging citizens into a collective low-cost observation strategy; and iii) the testing of spatially refined hydrodynamics and sediment transport model results (CROCO, WW3, MUSTANG) against *in situ* surveys and SSC products in order to simulate future trajectories of the LIL under different climate change scenarios.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

1. Communities

This LIL in particular is likely to be the one in which the usefulness of marinas could be demonstrated. Marinas could be acting as citizen scientists.

The main idea is to elevate an existing project (Phenomer) in 2 ways: with the integration of a new community (marina) and adding cost-effective sensors.

A well-structured stakeholder community is present and piloted through the GIP Seine Aval (www.seine-aval.fr). Among others there are HAROPA (Rouen and Le Havre port authorities), Water agency (Agence de l'eau Seine Normandie) and natural reserve.

In that LIL, LandSeaLot could also consider helping the marina Le Havre to understand its own environment in the context of its own concern/challenge, dredging in that case (a meeting with sailing harbour authorities already help to roughly present possible actions).

There are other communities which could be considered, such as Sogestran a marine and river transport company in Le Havre.

Finally, the links with the LandSeaLot Citizens Empowerment were approached.

- a. *Extension to additional community (marinas here) using an established citizen science activity (Phenomer)*

Biological parameter: the part below would address the primary production and phytoplankton bloom challenges of the LIL.

There is the crowdsourcing citizen science project named Phenomer run by Ifremer, on the detection of colored micro-algae blooms (<https://www.phenomer.org/>).

Within Phenomer, citizen scientists take pictures of colored blooms via a mobile application and eventually water samples. The system to treat the samples is in place with scientific labs available to perform the analyses. Phenomer is a project that runs since few years, it started in Brittany and has been extended to the whole French coast. Tania Hernandez works in Normandie and is involved in the Seine area. She is Romaric's contact at Phenomer for LandSeaLot purposes. Until now, the marinas are not involved in Phenomer, and Tania was interested in engaging with them as it could be a good way to enlarge the network and the observations.

Mel has been in contact with a strategic enthusiastic person (Julien Lebas) and asked him questions to try to map his stakeholders, who we could engage and how, what are the opportunities with cost-effective sensors, etc...

From the marinas in the area, only le Havre replied so far, so possibly others could be engaged.

Sailors already expressed concerns about the blooms they noticed, which shows a level of interest. Additionally, sailors would be good at this exercise as they are familiar with the colors of their waters compared to public citizen scientists.

b. Extension to additional parameters using cost-effective sensors by the community (marinas) in the established citizen science activity

If we consider that citizen science activities in the marinas are equipped with cost-effective sensors, it would be interesting for the LIL questions that they collect data on the biological parameters fluorescence and chlorophyll-a and on physical parameters temperature, salinity and turbidity. The physical parameters would be interesting to address the LIL questions on sediments dynamics and sediments morphology as there is a poor monitoring network with only a few points.

Comment post-interview:

From the KOM, nutrients measurements from manual kit are interesting to be evaluated and if efficient in our system deployed from our local LCE community. In particular as nutrients are a key issue in the Seine LSI.

Also strongly interested in testing PML radiometers as we will have strong actions in ocean color remote sensing. We should also have a 3y postdoc (not funded by LandSeaLot but with activities falling directly in our topic of interest) interested to conduct and analyze these observations.

c. Extension to additional area (location) and citizens challenge using cost-effective sensors by the community (marinas) in the established citizen science activity or others.

The harbor of Le Havre had been given the permission of dredging, which resuspends contaminants in the sediments and is costly. This is a concern for the marinas in Le Havre area. If the marinas sailors use cost-effective sensors to measure parameters in the estuary and outside, they could also monitor in the marinas, in the port.

LandSeaLot would not be able to use the data, as they do not work at this small scale, but they could offer their services to help the marina to analyse and interpret the data they collect, to put it into context (more or less turbidity events, sediments resuspensions) to understand them.

However, LandSeaLot would have no direct implication on the dredging scheme, nothing on operational scheme.

There are potentially other citizen science initiatives that could join the marinas effort, as Le Havre works with a conservation company that conducts the testing. The company which

likely has some competence in the area, could potentially be an intermediate. They could be involved in the citizen science initiatives mapping exercise.

d. *Other communities with potential.*

Sogestran group, river and maritime shipping company (<https://www.sogestran.com/en/>) has as a priority quality, security and respect for the environment. Sogestran has a strong connection with Le Havre municipality and other recreational activities. They could potentially embarked ferryboxes but they demand human resources and maintenance. This is outside the scope of LandSeaLot.

Marinas based in commercial ports managed areas have a more collective dynamic which is the case in Le Havre. To engage them we would need to know what their interest and needs are first.

e. *LandSeaLot Citizens Empowerment Forum and stakeholders*

Sogestran group could be considered for the LCE.

Every other year, there is a racing event gathering half a million visitors in Le Havre (Transat Jacques Vabre). It is a good place to showcase the citizen science activities in the area, to raise awareness. Sogestran offered a spot for science already in the village, Lucie has contacts.

Local stakeholders of the LIL, such as water agencies, port authorities in the estuary, already showed interest in cost-effective sensors to collect more data when Romaric contacted them. Once a sensor catalogue is available the discussion could be followed up with them.

2. **Cost-effective sensors**

The idea of evaluating cost-effective sensors, particularly for EOVs is mentioned.

a. *Evaluation of the cost-effective sensors quality*

Option1:

Ifremer, DYNECO/DHYSED (Romaric's lab) submitted a proposal to have ship time as follows, the sensors could be evaluated against traditional instruments onboard the vessel.

-4 oceanography campaigns every year (Feb-March, Apr-May and summer, Sept-Oct)

-3 location types visited:

- in the estuary where the turbidity is max.,
- close to the mouth estuary very close to Le Havre harbor, transition area between estuary and coastal sea/bay
- in the bay away from the direct estuary influence, with low physical impact on the sediments but high biological impact.

-Measurements during a full 12h tidal cycle at each location: water samples every hour surface and bottom, instrumented vertical casts every 30min. Additional samples or measurements can be considered as there is still room for complementary measurements.

Option2:

If the proposal requesting ship time is not accepted, for the sediment there is another option: at DYNECO/DHYSED, there are facilities to reproduce homogeneous suspension used to evaluate commercial sensors. The lab facilities could be used to evaluate cost-effective sensors on turbidity. If necessary, nutrients and chl_a low-cost solutions could also be

evaluated in lab, to be discussed.

b. *Cost-effective sensors need*

Turbidity:

Turbidity could be assessed with Secchi disks or with optical turbidity sensors with a different accuracy.

*Secchi disk--> Secchi depth can be a proxy for turbidity.

Ifremer is not using Secchi disks for its measurements, but SHOM (French National Hydrographic and Oceanographic Services) is and has a large database of Secchi depths. SHOM has set a relationship between Secchi depths and turbidity which is highly site-dependant.

If Secchi disks were to be deployed in the LIL area, they could start a database of Secchi depths and establish a relationship between secchi depths and turbidity for the area.

*Optical turbidity sensor--> It could be interesting to deploy in the LIL if any is available.

3. Data landscape

Phenomer has already a data flow in place, that seems to be based essentially on the Phenomer website and mobile application, meaning citizens, labs, scientists find info and data on the website.

LandSeaLot could support Phenomer, if they are interested in having their data more widely and openly accessible on EMODnet for example. A discussion needs to take place with Phenomer leaders here too.

Marinas are interested in having info they collect on a dashboard, but perhaps blooms are not suitable for a dashboard, if other parameters are collected it might be of interest though.

LIL Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary interview with Yoana Voynova (Hereon) and Anouk Blauw (DELTAIRES) on 02 May 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Maria Nordström (SMHI), Rachele Bordoni (ETT), Mikael Stenström (SMHI)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary (WSRE): The Wadden Sea and adjacent rivers experienced major changes in carbon and nutrient dynamics over the past four decades. Recent research showed that these variables are still changing. Using observation and modelling capabilities from three different RIs (ICOS-ERIC, DANUBIUS-RI, JERICO-RI), this LIL will showcase how enhanced data-model integration (*in situ* and remote sensing) across the LSI provides improved estimates of lateral carbon and nutrient fluxes and stocks. Thereby it will contribute to the development of a coastal water component in ICOS-ERIC, linking to collaboration plans developed in WP2 and pilot methods for integrating satellite data in WP3 models. River nutrient and carbon data will be evaluated and made available in an open-source data format in WP6. This area is also included in the EDITO-Model Lab project.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

SOOP (Shaping an Ocean Of Possibilities for science-industry collaboration) is a German project between 3 research centers (GEOMAR, AWI and Hereon), PI is Toste Tanhua (GEOMAR). A component of the project is for citizen scientists, e.g. sail boats, ships of opportunity. <http://www.soop-platform.earth/projekt/>

A discussion with SOOP will be set up.

The EU-funded AQUARIUS project (Aquatic Research Infrastructure Services for the health and protection of our unique, oceans, seas and freshwater ecosystems) offers free access to state-of-the-art research infrastructure across Europe to undertake collaborative research. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101130915>). Hereon and Deltares are partners in AQUARIUS.

1. Communities

SOOP could be considered as a citizen science initiative, as the sensors are deployed on sailing boats (all sizes are considered). A link with marinas would be interesting.

FerryBox-like systems in general use already existing water intakes that can divert the flow of water for their needs. On sailing boats, we need smaller and simpler versions of the FerryBox, due to the limited space available, and the citizen science component (requiring a simpler flow-through solution). This represents a new development within SOOP (SailingBox) by Hereon.

Shipping groups or communities could be approached on the Netherland side of the LIL.

SOOP, via GEOMAR also works with a company selling instruments to ships. This connection could be investigated.

In this LIL, there is a need to collect observations closer to the coast. The use of sailing boats could be considered with an initiative similar to Phenomer (citizen science initiative in France in which sailors are taking water samples later on analysed by engaged labs). The sampling

flow could perhaps be replicated in the Wadden Sea. <https://www.phenomer.org/> Nutrients and carbon are the parameters of interest, in general difficult to measure with low-cost sensors.

2. **Low-cost tech**

- Synergies between LandSeaLot and SOOP project:

Hereon is involved in technology development for communication to sensors. Hereon also has development related to the users of this communication to sensors on sail boats with deployment on small boat in the German Bight. For the development of the communication to sensors, Hereon works with a company providing low-cost sensors, Atlas scientific (<https://atlas-scientific.com/>) to have an application showing that the comm developed works. Any other company could be used. SOOP could consider using some LandSeaLot purchased sensors to do the test. So far Hereon focusses on temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, turbidity and optical application, but no carbon as usually the sensors are expensive. The list of parameters can be expanded, pH could be interesting. Relatively low-cost pH solutions are currently investigated.

With regard to data transfer (from sensors onto aggregators like EMODnet), other WPs/partners should be involved in the discussion (e.g. Toste Tanhua). So far there is no final destination for the data identified. There might not be a lot of data but it would be a good showcase for LandSeaLot to facilitate the dataflow of SOOP data towards aggregators.

Other developments at Hereon are work on surface drifters, biodegradable.

- Testbed to test sensors- linkage with AQUARIUS project

In the LIL, there is a land-based station named Cuxhaven that could be used to test sensors. Hereon is testing their instruments there before embarking them on vessels. It is an ICOS-D station. There are also possibilities to test radiometers, to be investigated though. It is a very turbid station, so turbidity could be tested but it might also be possible to put the instruments in the water directly.

Cuxhaven is also part of the AQUARIUS project, AQUARIUS funding could be used to test sensors in Cuxhaven, 3 partners need to apply for it. There is also a test site at Hereon, a river water station, also part of AQUARIUS. Underwater noise is also an option.

In addition, within AQUARIUS another station is available near Hereon (10 min walk), the Tesperhude Research Station, located on the Elbe River, it has a number of instruments available (https://hereon.de/central_units/research_infrastructure/tesperhude/index.php.en).

In AQUARIUS, Hereon participates with the use of the FerryBox, but this station can be also used as platform for sensor deployment & testing. Finally, Hereon offers in AQUARIUS the use of their shallow water vessel, either the *RV Ludwig Prandtl*, or the new *RV Coriolis* vessel (coming in late 2024) in the shallow waters of the LIL.

- Tidal flat area:

There is also the idea of setting up a light fixed station in a tidal flat area where most of the biological activities take place. In the Wadden Sea, the tidal flat areas are numerous, and it is legally difficult to set up anything there and complex. However, there is a project from the University Twente with an organised site and boat in a tidal flat area, that could be contacted to further investigate the possibility of cooperation and sensor installation.

Detection of algal with optical sensors is not appropriate in this region of the Wadden Sea because of the high turbidity.

3. **Data landscape**

The topic was not discussed during the interview.

LIL Tagus and Sado estuaries System interview

with Francisco Campuzano (+Atlantic)
on 20 March 2024

Presence: Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Melanie Symes (TEM), Giulia Dapueto (ETT), Rachele Bordoni (ETT)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

Tagus and Sado estuaries System (TSS): This LIL will focus on heat waves and flooding effects making full use of low-cost sensors (temperature and water level) to fill gaps along the LSI and quantify impacts on the local ecosystem and hence on the ecosystem services provided to the benefit of society. It will be supported by the engagement of citizen organisations, marinas and local stakeholders. The satellite observations will be integrated with data from numerical models and low-cost sensors aimed to improve resolution and accuracy.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

There are 2 estuaries in the LIL. The Tagus one is a typical estuary with a big river going out, with a large bay. The Sado estuary has a river coming from the south, so the flow is low. It has a population of dolphins. It is a coastal lagoon linked to an estuary linked to the ocean. In terms of biodiversity, they are very different estuaries. There are more oysters in the Sado estuary than in the Tagus one because it presents more marine conditions.

There are marine protected areas and marine reserves in the LIL.

Fig 1: LIL area with the Tagus estuary in the north and the Sado estuary in the south.

1. Communities

- Aquaculture parks:

Aquaculture pools are present in various areas in the LIL (Fig1). Sensors could be deployed attached to the oyster parks structures, nets for instance.

-->North of the LIL, in the Tagus estuary (Fig 2).

Fig 2

--> South of the LIL, in the Sado estuary, south of Pontes (Fig 3)

Fig 3

South of Setubal, there is also a tower where sensors can be deployed (circled on the map Fig 4). At the moment, there are no sensors running at the tower.

Figure 4

There are also small boats in the area with man-made docks, such as outside Faralhão (Fig5). The area will be further investigated.

Fig 5

Some aquaculture producers have been approached and are very interested in deploying sensors. Establishing contacts with the producers is on an ad-hoc basis and depends on the type of producers, recreational versus professional.

The Portuguese association of aquaculture will also be contacted. Meetings are taking place in Setúbal, as it is in the center of Portugal about every 6 months, next one is in May.

From previous project, e.g. YTIDE, +Atlantic were providing simple messages to the farmers to inform them when (depending on tidal conditions) and how (meteorologic conditions) to work and visit the park with their boats in order to optimised their working time. The messages are based on models' outputs which could be improved with more data from strategic places.

- Marinas and ports

There are marinas in the areas from the ocean (for instance in Caiscais, outside of the Targus estuary) to inside the estuaries. Many of the marinas are managed by the port of Lisbon in the Tagus estuary and by the port of Setúbal in the Sado estuary. South of the Sado estuary, there is the longest handmade dock built by fisherman (Fig 6).

Fig 6

There is an association for the marinas, the Portuguese Association of Ports and Marinas (APPR), <http://www.marinasdeportugal.pt/en/>. APPR organised the prestigious International Council of Marine Industry (ICOMIA- <https://www.icomia.org/>) World Marinas Conference on 9-11 October 2023 in Algarve.

There are 7 marinas groups in in the APPR, a couple could be approached.

The port of Lisbon has been contacted via a project named FOCCUS. Some marinas in the area have been delivered a 'blue flag', therefore they have to perform some monitoring. The port of Lisbon showed interest in LandSeaLot to facilitate the monitoring performance of the marinas with 'blue flag'. It is however unclear if the marinas will be keen on joining TransEurope Marinas, this needs further investigation.

The contact with the port of Lisbon is more bureaucratic and structured, documented information on LandSeaLot has already been provided for discussion at the port board.

There are ferry ports in both estuaries. Some interactions started before the pandemics, but since nothing concrete.

Nautical stations also have their own network, that we can engage with.

- Portuguese environmental Agency

The agency runs the river monitoring service and is responsible for the Water Framework Directive. Communication is established since August 2023, and the first meeting was in December 2023. There are few rather big rivers other than the Tagus and Sado that are reaching the estuaries and there is a need to have near real time water level data for the rivers and for the tides around the estuaries. The agency has a few stations but not enough (due to lack of resources some were discontinued). A co-planning with the Agency to identify the locations of the stations to set up (or to start running again) with the LandSeaLot sensors would be ideal. And all data would be shared with the Agency.

- Company performing monitoring for hotel complexes in Troia, south of Setubal

In Troia, hotel complexes are developing, a company was hired to perform some environmental monitoring of the area. Data is collected. No contact has been established yet.

2. Low-cost tech

- Temperature

The Electric Blue CRL temperature sensors are interesting for this LIL, it can be attached to oyster bags outside of Setubal for example. The loggers would be deployed in the intertidal area. The oysters need to be submerged for part of the day. So the loggers measure air temperature and water temperature but if the tidal gauges and the model are used, the

temperatures can be differentiated. The transitional waters are under monitored and in the model, there is a huge gradient in temperature. 50-100 sensor units would be interesting to cover the gap. To collect the data, field campaigns could be arranged every 3 months, it would also be an opportunity to show the farmers how to collect the data and if they are comfortable with the collection they can do the collection themselves.

Temperature is needed for the marine heat waves.

Along the Tagus, there are some buoys that can be used to evaluate the temperature sensors. A pressure sensor in the shape of the Temperature logger from Electric Blue CRL (size of a magnet) would be very helpful too, if it exists in low-cost.

- Water level

Water level is needed for the flooding topic, the river input and for the tides, with a sensor stuck under a bridge, with near real time data. Perhaps a couple of instruments in real time in the rivers to address the needs of the Portuguese environmental Agency and some others near real time for the tides. There are 2 tidal ecologies in the area, almost outside of the estuaries. The water level sensors data would be used to validate the models. The sensors could be evaluated using the tide gauges in place as reference stations, one in Caiscai, one owned by the port of Lisbon.

From experience with other projects, the maintenance of the instruments is essential (once or twice a year) to ensure that data are coming in.

- Testbed

South of Setubal, there is the structure of a tower that can be used to install sensors and test them. Fig 7 is the boat used to reach the tower.

Fig 7

The LIL could be used as a benchmark to test sensors in real conditions. Clear skies ease the comparison with earth obs data. There is easy access to the sea and the river via public transport, Lisbon-Setubal is an hour's train ride.

- Feedback to the developers

Developers often try to develop devices that mimic classical/traditional instruments with cheaper materials. But some areas need specific shapes and outside of the box thinking. For instance, the intertidal areas need specifically adapted device designs. LandSeaLot could give feedback on that info to interested developers. The LIL participants could be providing the needs of the experts in observation, users of cost-effective equipments.

3. Data Landscape

+Atlantic is a data provider, aggregator with knowledge on how to format the data, analyse it. It has an ERDDAP service working for the rivers and other sources can be added.

LIL Danube delta and coastal area interview **with Irina Stanciu and Adrian Stanica (GeoEcoMar)** **on 20 May 2024**

Presence: Patrick Gorringer (SMHI), Emilie Breviere (SMHI), Mikael Stenström (SMHI)

Interview video recorded for internal purpose.

Extract from proposal:

Danube Delta and coastal area (DD): This LIL will focus on the coastal sediment budget development under combined human/climate pressures and inputs of pollutants from the Danube River to the North-West Black Sea through the delta. With its facilities and established stakeholder communities and in synergy with ongoing projects in the area (H2020 CERTO and H2020 DOORS), DANUBIUS-RI will support the action to fill observation gaps, thus integrating information from numerical models at the coastal scale and from catchment *in situ* and remote sensing data.

Points of discussion, output will contribute to 2 deliverables in M6:

1. Citizen Science/communities
2. Low-cost tech
3. Data Landscape

Minutes:

The Romanian coast is split into 2 distinct parts. The northern part is the Danube delta coast which features over 160km of natural sanctuary with 3 remote villages and no road. The southern part is the most anthropic part of the entire Black Sea, very touristic with the Constanza town.

The LIL is located in the northern part.

1. Communities

The LIL being essentially a nature reserve, it has no marinas. The citizen science activities with school kids that the LIL leaders have experienced with are located in the southern part of the Romanian coast, and so not within the LIL area.

In the LIL area, the population is scarce, there are one city Sulina and few villages with fishermen. There is a high school in Sulina, discussion could take place with the teachers and be trained.

In villages, few enthusiastic people have put in place NGOs to educate kids and raise awareness. The remote villages could be engaged in LandSeaLot activities depending on budget availability.

Every summer for many years, the LIL leads visit the area with the coastal measurement team. They have an established trust relationship with the local communities in place.

An ideal approach would be for the LIL leads to check out with the locals the list of cost-effective sensors available and their basic characteristics this summer in order to assess together what is interesting and feasible. Then once the selection is made, the locals would

need a training exercise on site in one of the remote villages of the south of the Danube delta (one day to reach the place).

The willingness and support of the locality of Jurilovka was mentioned.

2. Low-cost tech

In terms of parameters, in the LIL there are very few historical data. A coastal station has been installed by GeoEcoMar which is part of the Danube delta Supersite of DANUBIUS RI. It provides data on physical, chemical and biological parameters. However, some parameters need a higher density of data and some parameters are missing.

- Water level variation is of interest, in particular for the short events of high intensity in location where there are no marigraphs. This may be measured using mounted cameras that take photos. This would contribute to the LIL work on modeling short episodic flood events.

- Onset of algal blooms is of interest in those very productive waters.

- Salinity is another very important parameter, with turbidity, temperature and chlorophyll-a as they provide info on the variability of the long jetty at Sulina, the upwelling currents and on general water circulation in the area impacting the environment.

- Microplastics in sediments and marine litter are also interesting, in connection with a DOORS experiment run in June in all Black Sea countries. DOORS is an EU project linking science, policy and industry for critical Black Sea regeneration that started in 2021 and will end in May 2025.

Plastic pollution is high in the LIL even in remote pristine beaches. The plastic is brought up by ships and/or the Danube River. A toolkit to collect plastic would be of interest.

Near real time data is not a requirement for looking at the water circulation, mostly due to the lack of staff assistance onsite to ensure that all is functioning according to plan.

Validation was also raised.

3. Data Landscape

The topic was not discussed during the interview.